

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PRINCIPAL SUPERVISION AND
INTER-PERSONAL COMMUNICATION WITH THE PERFORMANCE
OF THE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN BUKIT BATU
DISTRICT, PALANGKARAYA CITY, INDONESIA**

**Andrew Hizkia Siman,
Sulaiman,
Rustam Effendiⁱ**

Master of Education Management Program,
Lambung Mangkurat University,
Indonesia

Abstract:

Teachers have to participate actively in formatting reliable human resources in the field of education and set down his capacity as professionals, following the demands of a growing community. Today the quality of education in elementary school in Bukit Batu district has not met the standard that has been set. It is due to the performance of the teacher. For instance, teachers teach with improper planning, the implementation learning which has not been optimal and the technique of evaluation is inappropriate. Therefore it is important to find out any factors that can influence the performance of the teacher. This study is aimed to determine: (1) the correlation between principal's supervision and the performance of teacher in elementary school in Bukit Batu district, (2) the correlation between teacher's interpersonal communication and the performance of teacher in elementary school in Bukit Batu district, (3) the simultaneous correlation of principal's supervision and interpersonal communication of teacher toward the performance of elementary school in Bukit Batu district. The method used is descriptive method with the correlation technique. The population of this study is 136 teachers of the elementary school in Bukit Batu district, Palangkaraya City. By using the proportional random sampling technique it was obtained 102 teachers as the sample. A Likert scale questionnaire was a technique used to collect the data of the variable of principal's supervision, teacher's interpersonal communication and teacher's performance. The instrument test was conducted by using the validity test and reliability of data, while the normality test and linearity one were used to examine the requirement test of data analysis. To determine the correlation between each variable of the study, it was conducted by using product moment Pearson correlation and multiple correlations with the application program of SPSS 20.00. The results of this study show that: (1) there is a correlation between the supervision of principal and teacher's

ⁱ Correspondence: email jurnalulm@gmail.com

performance of elementary school in Bukit Batu district, (2) there is a correlation between teacher's interpersonal communication and teacher's performance of elementary school in Bukit Batu district, (3) there is a simultaneous correlation of the principal's supervision and interpersonal communication of teacher toward the performance of elementary school in Bukit Batu district. Based on the results it is suggested to: (1) the principal in order to be able to provide guidance to teachers in constructing lesson plan, carry out class visitation, lead teachers about the way to assess student progress, (2) teachers in order to provide instructional materials in accordance with the curriculum, implement the session plan that has been prepared, guide students having problems in learning.

Keywords: supervision of the principal, teacher interpersonal communication, the performance of teacher

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Law number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system states that national education aims to educate the nation's life and develop Indonesian people as a whole, namely devoted people to God Almighty, noble character who has knowledge and skills, physical and spiritual health, a solid and independent personality and a sense of community and national responsibility.

The success of the national education goals must pay attention to the components of education, especially human resources, which have a very important role in determining the success of schools to realize educational goals. Because the teacher is the spearhead of the learning process in school, the quality and number of teachers need to be improved and developed according to current and future needs. The principal also plays an important role in advancing education related to teacher supervision and guidance.

The role of the teacher's performance originating from the principal can be accommodated in supervision activities. The supervision of the principal to the teacher is intended so that the teachers always strive to improve their personal and professional abilities (Mantja, 2007). Supervision is also intended as a medium of communication between teachers and principals, especially when teachers need help in overcoming difficulties and obstacles faced in carrying out their duties. Professional teachers are teachers who have the following characteristics: (1) have the ability as experts in the field of educating and teaching, (2) having a sense of responsibility that is having commitment and concern for their duties, and (3) having a sense of duty and living their duties as a life career and uphold the teacher's code of ethics (Sahertian, 2000).

Supervision is one of the functions of principals whose goal is to improve teacher performance in carrying out teaching. Through effective supervision, the Principal can control, foster, encourage and motivate teachers to carry out their higher quality tasks.

But based on the facts, supervision activities have not been implemented effectively, both in the implementation mechanism, the implementation of the results of supervision and in terms of the ability or professionalism of the implementers/supervisors.

Supervision carried out by the principal is expected to have an impact on the teacher in carrying out his work to achieve maximum results in the learning process and not experience any more problems in the teaching process carried out. The purpose of the supervision is to the teacher as the main key in carrying out the teaching and learning process because without the teacher the supervision process will not run well. So from that supervision should be able to help and direct in various things that occur in the KBM process.

Teachers who have a good perception of teaching supervision, the teacher will try to receive advice and input supervisors to improve teaching, because supervision means teacher guidance towards improvement in teaching. The opposite is true if advice and advice from supervisors are ignored by the teacher so that it can have an impact on poor teaching activities. This is related to teacher satisfaction, namely the teacher's expectations of the principal with the reality given by him. If the teacher's expectations are by the rewards given by the principal it is likely that the teacher will be satisfied. Rewards here are not only material aspects such as salary increases, allowances or honorariums but also spiritual matters such as the principal's attention, good communication between the teacher and the principal, encouragement/motivation by the principal (Bafadal, 2004).

In addition to supervising the principal, another thing that can affect teacher performance is communication between teachers. Communication is a very basic thing in human life. Simple communication can occur if there are similarities between the messenger and the recipient of the message (Rohim, 2009). Moor defines communication as conveying understanding between individuals. According to him, every human being is based on the capacity to convey intentions, desires, feelings, knowledge, and experiences from one person to another (Rohim, 2009).

Teacher performance is greatly influenced by many factors, including teacher professionalism, teacher welfare, working environment conditions, supervision, and so on. Supervision as an effort to develop the teacher's ability to be a more professional person, if implemented effectively will greatly affect its performance, namely the improvement of the quality of the learning process in the classroom. For this goal to be achieved, supervision must be carried out effectively and professional supervisors are needed.

Based on the initial survey on 13 August 2013 by visiting several elementary schools in Bukit Batu district, problems related to teachers seen in the field have a tendency, among others: still being met by teachers who are slow in carrying out teaching assignments, who are still absent teachers at the time teaching, still found by teachers who do not understand the rules of learning, are still found by teachers who feel indifferent to the field of work and still difficult coordination between teachers in

carrying out their duties. Besides, with the teacher's interests (for example: delivering children who are still in kindergarten or elementary school), the intensity of teacher arrivals in schools is decreasing. The teacher after completing learning immediately returns home for many reasons, leaving aside social relations with fellow teachers in the school. This resulted in a lack of motivation for teachers to improve the quality of learning.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Principal Supervision

Supervision is guidance for someone to be able to carry out their duties properly and can provide benefits to people who are supervised. Educational supervision is defined as the process of providing professional assistance services to teachers to improve their ability to carry out the tasks of managing the learning process effectively and efficiently (Bafadal, 2007). One of the supervision carried out must have planning, implementation, and evaluation of the results of supervision.

Supervision is an effort to provide services and assistance to teachers both individually and in groups to improve the teaching of the Ministry of Education (Sahertian, 2004). What is meant by the supervision of the principal is that all supervision activities carried out by the principal as a planned effort to provide guidance, guidance, and service so that the teachers increase their professional skills, can become better teachers and produce better students as well.

As for the indicators relating to the principal supervising variable in this study based on Permendiknas Number 13 of 2007 are as follows: (1) guiding teachers in preparing syllabi for each subject, (2) guiding teachers in choosing and using strategies/methods/techniques learning, (3) guiding teachers in preparing lesson plans, (4) guiding teachers in carrying out learning activities, (5) guiding teachers in managing and caring for, using and using educational media and learning facilities, (6) motivating teachers to utilize information technology in learning.

A. Interpersonal Communication of Teachers

Communication activity is the process of activities carried out by someone who will be realized through delivery and acceptance both as a source and recipient of information that can occur vertically or horizontally. The interpersonal communication of teachers in this study is teacher communication which is divided into two sub-variables. First, vertical communication, namely communication that flows from the teacher to the leading elements in the school. This communication includes: (a) suggestions/ideas, (b) feelings and thoughts, (c) reports on work results, (d) needs. Communication from the leadership element includes: (e) thought instruction in the work, (f) the rationale in the work, (g) policies, (h) expressing work assessment, (i) developing a sense of duty. Second, horizontal communication, communication between peers (teachers), includes: (a) coordination of assignments and information on planned activities, (b) support and

joint problem solving, (c) conflict resolution, (d) gaining understanding with Wayne and Don Faulos (Mulyasa, 2007).

B. Teacher Performance

Performance or work performance is interpreted as an expression of ability based on knowledge, attitudes, skills, and motivation in producing something. Therefore the teacher's performance is interpreted as the workability of a teacher which is seen from the level of achievement, and the completion of the tasks that are his responsibility, by the conditions set in a field of work. Teacher performance can be seen and measured based on specifications/competency criteria that must be possessed by each teacher. In connection with teacher performance, according to Uno (2009), the form of behavior in question is teacher activities including: 1) Quality of work which includes: (a) planning learning programs, (b) explaining subject matter, (c) assessing learning outcomes, (d) applying research results in learning; 2) Speed/accuracy of work which includes: (a) applying things new in learning, (b) giving teaching material according to the characteristics of students, (c) completing teaching programs according to the academic calendar; 3) Initiatives in work which include: (a) using media in learning, (b) using various methods in learning, (c) administering the school well, (d) creating new things in managing school administration; 4) Work capabilities which include: (a) being able to lead the class, (b) being able to manage IBM, (c) being able to analyze the results assessment of student learning, (d) mastering the foundation of education; 5) Communication which includes: (a) carrying out tutoring services, (b) communicating new things in learning, (c) using various techniques in learning manage the learning process, (d) openly accept input for improving learning.

2. Methods

2.1 Research Design

This research aims to find out the relationship between school principal supervision variables (X1), teacher interpersonal communication (X2) on teacher performance (Y). Based on the characteristics of the problem to be studied, this study aims to determine the correlation of independent variables to the dependent variable (Sugiyono, 2007).

2.2 Research Populations and Samples

The intended population is the total number of homogeneous members. The population of this study was all teachers of the elementary school in Bukit Batu district, Palangkaraya City, which were spread across 7 public high schools that met the following criteria: (1) Teachers who have S1 education qualifications, (2) The teacher has a minimum of 5 years working period. Elementary School Teachers in Bukit Batu Subdistrict have an average S1 education qualification. The number of representative samples that the researchers used was based on those developed by Isaac and Michael with an error rate of 5% so the sample in the study was 102 teachers from a total of 136

teachers (Sugiyono, 2010). In determining the sample of each school so that it is proportional to the size represented, then the elementary school with many teachers has many representatives, while the elementary schools with a small number of teachers have little representation.

2.3 Research Instruments

This study uses an instrument in the form of a questionnaire. As for the questionnaire used is a closed questionnaire, respondents chose answers that were by the answer choices that were following the real situation, namely capturing data from respondents regarding the supervision of principals and interpersonal communication between teachers and teacher performance of the elementary school in Bukit Batu district.

2.4 Data Collection Techniques

The technique of collecting data uses questionnaires/questionnaires in the form of written questions that will be answered by the teachers who are sampled in each teacher in elementary school in Bukit Batu district.

2.5 Data Analysis Techniques

Discussion in the form of descriptive statistics, with two kinds of data testing processes. First, testing requirements analysis includes normality tests and linearity tests. Second, is the calculation of hypothesis testing using the F test.

3. Results

3.1 Normality Test

Based on the results of calculations obtained a significant level of 0.200 for the supervision of the principal, then 0.289 for teacher interpersonal communication and 0.252 for teacher performance. Based on the significant level obtained it turns out to be greater than 0.05, so it can be said that the significant level of the principal supervision variable, teacher interpersonal communication variables, and teacher performance are normally distributed.

3.2 Linearity Test

Based on the results of the linearity test there are two observed relationships, namely the relationship between the Principal Supervision variable (X1) and the Teacher Performance variable (Y) and the relationship between Teacher Interpersonal Communication variables (X2) and Teacher Performance variables (Y). The first relationship between school supervision and teacher performance has a linear relationship with the R-Square value = 0.694. The second relationship between teacher interpersonal communication and teacher performance was also assessed linearly with the R-Square value = 0.129.

3.3 Hypothesis Testing

Based on the results of calculations, it is known that the correlation coefficient of supervising the principal with the teacher's performance in elementary school in Bukit Batu district Regency is $r_{y1} = 0.938$ and $p < 0.01$ (positive and significant correlation), thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is a relationship between the supervision of the principal and the teacher's performance in elementary school in Bukit Batu district.

Based on the results of calculations, it is known that the correlation coefficient of interpersonal communication between teachers and teacher performance in elementary school in Bukit Batu district is $r_{y2} = 0.554$ and $p < 0.01$ (positive and significant correlation), thus H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is a relationship between teacher interpersonal communication and teacher performance.

Based on the calculation results it is known that the price of the R_{y12} double correlation = 0.967; $p < 0.01$ greater than individual correlation $r_{y1} = 0.938$; $p < 0.01$ and $r_{y2} = 0.554$; $p < 0.01$. Based on the price of $F_{\text{value}} = 901,284$; $p < 0.01$ greater than $F_{\text{table}} (F_{0.05 (2) (125)} = 3.08)$.

Thus the hypothesis which reads there is no relationship between the supervision of the principal and teacher interpersonal communication together with the teacher's performance of the elementary school in Bukit Batu district is rejected. This means that there is a relationship between the supervision of the principal and teacher interpersonal communication together with the teacher's performance.

4. Discussion

4.1 Relationship between Principal Supervision (X1) and Teacher Performance (Y)

Based on the findings obtained from the answers of the teachers who were made respondents in this study showed that the supervision of the principal of the Public Elementary School in the Bukit Batu Sub-District of Palangkaraya City, Central Kalimantan Province was in the moderate category. Supervision carried out in the State Elementary School of Bukit Batu Subdistrict, Palangkaraya has several functions, namely as an effort made by the principal in order to foster teachers so that the quality of the learning process and results increases and strives for teachers to improve performance so that they can adjust to the demands of the profession. In other words, the function of supervision is to strive to develop professional competence for teachers in carrying out their teaching duties. This finding reinforces the opinion of Sudjana (2008) that the supervision activities carried out by principals are not just routine activities, but there are several objectives to be achieved, among others: (1) As an activity to improve the quality of learning, (2) changes to the elements related to learning, (3) as lead and guide activities.

Supervision carried out by the principal is related to problem-solving rather than looking for problems together between the teacher and the principal. Principals who want to pay attention to and help teachers in solving teaching problems, personal problems, and professional problems will be able to give teachers satisfaction in their

work. The teacher will feel valued and cared for so that the teacher will be kind to the organization and the principal, and try to improve and improve their performance. These findings reinforce the opinion of Ametembun (2006) operational supervision objectives are: helping teachers to see clearly the purpose of education, helping teachers guide students in learning, helping teachers in using learning experience resources, helping teachers in using learning methods and tools modern, helps teachers to meet learning needs, helps teachers in assessing the student's achievement and the learning outcomes of the teacher's own work, helps the teacher in developing the mental reaction or work morale of the teacher in the context of growth, helps new teachers in the school so that they feel happy with the assignment helping teachers so that time and energy are fully devoted to fostering students in their schools. This finding also strengthens the results of Fauzi's (2007) research that there is a relationship between school principal supervision and teacher performance, between Work Motivation and Teacher performance, and on the relationship between supervision and work motivation together with teacher performance in Pilot Public Schools in Banjarmasin.

The implementation of supervision activities is carried out by the principal in guiding the teacher. This is because the teaching and learning process carried out by the teacher is the core of the overall education process with the teacher as the main role holder. The teaching and learning process is a process that contains a series of actions by teachers and students based on reciprocal relationships that take place in educational situations to achieve certain goals. This finding reinforces the opinion of Arikunto (2007) that the purpose of supervision is to improve the quality of the general situation of the school in such a way that it creates a calm and peaceful situation and is conducive to general school life, especially in the quality of learning that shows the success of graduates.

Principals as supervisors can perform their duties, functions, and responsibilities well, carry out effective and professional supervision of education, then the logic of providing supervision by the principal will improve teacher teaching performance. This finding supports the results of Noorman's (2008) research that there is a positive and significant relationship between Principal Supervision and teacher performance, between teacher work motivation and teacher performance, and between Principal Supervision and teacher work motivation with teacher performance in Sungai Tabuk District Middle School Kabupaten Banjar. Principal support using a partnership approach is very influential in improving the quality of teacher teaching performance. Thus from some of the descriptions above it can be concluded that there is a relationship between the supervision of the principal and the teacher's performance.

4.2 The Relationship between Teacher's Interpersonal Communication (X2) and Teacher's Performance (Y)

Based on the findings obtained from the teacher's answers made the respondents in this study indicate that interpersonal communication teachers of the State Elementary Schools in Bukit Batu Subdistrict, Palangkaraya City, Central Kalimantan Province are

in the moderate category. In the era of educational autonomy illustrated in school-based management, teachers have a significant role in seeking the progress of the learning process, namely the teacher's performance. Good relationships are needed among school components to improve work outcomes. This form of relationship is teacher-to-person communication. Interpersonal communication between teachers can take the form of asking experienced teachers, so that teacher knowledge will increase and work results increase. In this case, communication is the process of delivering information. Communication can be said to be successful if there are transfer and understanding of meaning from one person to another. An idea no matter how large it is, it will not be useful before it is passed on and understood by others. Communication can be through the mind and body language. If the teacher has communication skills, the teacher's performance will also increase. This reinforces the opinion of Chester Barnard (Panuju, 1997) saying that communication is a major force in forming organizations. Three main elements of the organization, one of which is communication, the other is organizational goals and willingness. For him, communication makes a dynamic system of cooperation with organizations and connects organizational goals to the participation of the people in them. These findings reinforce the opinion of Thoha (2008) also said that communication is very important in organizational behavior. Unfortunately, this very important communication can rarely be understood clearly so that it creates several obstacles. Communication is not just the process of delivering information whose symbols can be seen, heard and understood, but the process of delivering information as a whole is included in the feelings and attitudes of the people who convey the information.

With communication we form mutual understanding, foster friendship, nurture compassion and spread understanding. The existence of good communication results in high performance because problems that arise can be resolved well and can be solved together. The quality of communication is also determined by the analysis of objectives, reasoning, concerning things that are described or explained to others. The ability of the teacher to communicate will show a positive, trustworthy and open nature to colleagues or students. The quality of communication can also be realized through sound quality that is well played, meaning that teachers who have a clear voice, including good intonation and expression will make students and teachers listen and pay attention to the contents of the teacher's talk. This finding supports Fathurahman's (2010) research that there is a positive and significant relationship between communication activities and teacher work enthusiasm in one-roof elementary-junior high schools in Balangan Regency. Maisyarah (2011) concluded that there was a relationship between teacher interpersonal communication and teacher performance, between teacher job satisfaction and teacher performance, and between teacher interpersonal communication and teacher job satisfaction together with the performance of Madrasah Aliyah teachers in Banjarmasin City.

4.3 Relationship between Principal Supervision (X1) and Teacher Interpersonal Communication (X2) together with Teacher Performance (Y)

Based on the findings of the performance of state elementary school teachers in the Bukit Batu sub-district of Palangkaraya in sub variable 1) pedagogical competencies, 2) personality competencies, 3) social competencies, 4) professional competencies including the moderate category. Teachers who work at the Public Elementary School in the Bukit Batu District of Palangkaraya City can express work problems, express feelings and thoughts about work, give new suggestions or ideas about work, notify the tools needed when implementing learning to school leaders.

Likewise the principal is able to provide a job description, provide information about employment policies, explain the basic reasons for doing the work, give praise if the teacher does the task well, provide training information that will be followed by the teacher, give a warning to the teacher if make mistakes, support and provide an explanation of belonging to the task. The teacher will easily prepare the learning plan, deliver the subject matter he is teaching, he feels happy in carrying out the task. This finding supports the results of a study by Burhanudin (2011) which concluded that there was a positive relationship between supervision and teacher performance, between work motivation and teacher performance, and between supervision and work motivation together with junior high school teacher performance in South Hamlet District of Barito Regency South.

The Principal can assess the work performance of the teacher by looking at some of the results of his work, among others: in the planning, implementation and evaluation carried out by the teacher. This finding reinforces the opinion of Handoko (2007) defining performance appraisal or performance appraisal is the process of an organization evaluating or evaluating employee performance. This activity can relate to personnel decisions and provide feedback to employees about implementing their work. The usefulness of performance appraisal is as follows: (a) encourage people or employees to behave positively or improve their actions that are below the standard, (b) as an assessment material for management whether the employee has worked well and (c) provides the basis strong for organizational improvement policymaking.

Teachers who can coordinate tasks with peers, want to share information with peers if there is up-to-date information, provide solutions if friends experience difficulties, discuss employment problems, mediate if conflicts occur between friends, provide emotional and psychological support to peers. The teacher will be easy to plan to learn, able to carry out learning well and be able to properly assess Teachers who have good teaching skills, have high motivation and are supported by a good headmaster's leadership will improve their performance. This finding reinforces the opinion of Gibson, et al. (2002) that there are three sets of variables that influence work behavior and performance or performance, namely: (1) individual variables consist of: (a) abilities and skills, mental and physical, (b) background behind, among others: family, social level, payroll, (c) demographic includes: age, origin, gender; (2) organizational variables consisting of: (a) resources, (b) leadership, (c) rewards, (d)

structure, (e) job design; and (3) psychological variables consisting of: (a) perceptions, (b) attitude, (c) personality, (d) learning, (e) motivation.

Teachers who carry out tasks with priority to quality/results, complete tasks on time, feel proud of their duties and responsibilities, feel safe in carrying out their duties, the teacher will carry out learning with a sense of security, peace which in turn will achieve maximum results marked with increasing student achievement. This finding supports the results of a study by Karuhei (2012) which concluded that there was a relationship between principals managerial skills and teacher performance, between teacher work motivation and the performance of state junior high school teachers in Palangkaraya, and between principals managerial skills and teacher work motivation together with the performance of state junior high school teachers in Palangkaraya. Thus it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between the supervision of the principal and communication between teachers together with the teacher's performance in improving the learning and teaching process.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research conducted at elementary school in Bukit Batu district regarding the supervision of the principal and the interpersonal communication of the teacher with teacher performance, the following was obtained:

- 1) There is a relationship between the supervision of the principal and the teacher's performance in elementary school in Bukit Batu district.
- 2) There is a relationship between teacher-to-person communication with the teacher's performance of the elementary school in Bukit Batu district.
- 3) There is a relationship between the supervision of the principal and communication between teachers together with the teacher's performance in elementary school in Bukit Batu district.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the research conducted at elementary school in Bukit Batu district regarding the supervision of the principal and the communication between the teachers and the teacher's performance, it can be suggested as follows:

1. The principal of the elementary school in Bukit Batu district can be used as reference material to spur teachers to improve their performance. The principal should:
 - a. Guiding teachers in compiling and perfecting the RPP to fit the learning objectives.
 - b. Conduct class visits to assess the teacher's learning.
 - c. Guiding teachers about ways to assess student progress.
 - d. Provide learning aids needed by the teacher.
 - e. Give praise to the teacher who does the job well.

2. The elementary school in Bukit Batu district as a useful reference material to improve performance in carrying out their daily tasks. Teachers should:
 - a. Correcting and returning student work.
 - b. Actively attend learning seminars to be applied in the classroom.
 - c. Trying to provide learning materials referring to the latest learning resources according to the applicable curriculum.
 - d. Arrange learning materials according to the characteristics of students.
 - e. Hold a test at the beginning of the semester, to find out the characteristics of students
 - f. Discipline implementing the meeting plan that has been prepared, so that the teaching material is completely completed in that semester.
 - g. Prepare the class management administration books properly
3. The next study that examines problems that have relevance to this research problem as reference material and so that they are motivated to examine other variables that can contribute to the progress of schools in particular and the world of education in general.

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